

**DEMOCRACY AND IDENTITY CONFLICTS OF VARIOUS REGIONS: A STUDY OF LAST
FEW DECADES.**

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The perfections of modern values are of the same importance which have been there in the traditional one's like race, religion, linguistic and casteism. These forces are not just there in the society but have taken a solid state in society which sometimes provide a greater way to split the thought of nationalism. Democratic process has further progressed and widened this divide because of ethinisation of political space in which community and group identity has emerged far more powerful than already one. This is evident from increasing appeal of identity of various races in the societies during elections. Liberal democracy which was based on the premise that individuals are rational too much to decide their good and bad and would be voting after giving rational appraisal to policies have given way to the identity based polarisation in current situations. And as the identity is not a fixed or a given entity the political elites are engaged not only in consolidating which already exists but they are also digging up and manufacturing the new ones where it is required to fit into suits in competitive electoral politics. This paper explores how identity politics unfolds itself in democratic process and attempts to narrow the liberal political space through ethnic mobilisation in name of power share and protecting the group identity. It also delineates how ethinisation of nation states has come to challenge the very bases of liberal framework of political democracy in India more in previous two to three decades.

Whole world is engulfed in conflicts in one way or other way, our country also comes in the list, by this way or that way. Identity conflicts are on rise in the whole world!. Being negative in sense, the goals and achievements which societies want to see are far away to happen, as there are much more hindrances in the way of identity conflicts and others. The perception that the spread of means and message of modernity along with percolation of economic growth would diminish the primordial loyalties, sadly, has not come true. All the societies marked by diversity based on factors like religion, race, languages, sects and sub-sects or similar other elements are witness to this phenomenon which seems to have exploded exponentially in the last two decades. The premise that the Europe has moved beyond the question on nationality, and the ethno-nationalists quarrels and conflicts are restricted to pre-modern societies has proved wrong. The quantum of conflicts might have been different depending on the nature and magnitude of divide in the societies, but ethnic conflict is a harsh reality which all nation states are grappling with in some way or other. There are broadly three intended objectives of the ethnic conflicts emerging from claims. They are: Secessionism, territorial autonomy and greater inclusion and integration of their community demands in the system. The conflicts emerge from the minority community which feels deprived and neglected in the existing set up and therefore want a justified change which could ensure equal veritable space of all communities in the system in terms of representation, economic opportunities, civil and ethnic rights and so on. Thus, there is always a notion of victimhood, perceived or substantial that triggers and works behind the claims and conflicts. There are some conflicts in which the ethnic (cultural, religious or linguistic) minorities aim at independence as they want a separate part of land or we can say homeland for themselves, an ethno nationalist claim. There are others who do not seek secession but certainly want a larger control on the areas which they think should be exclusively controlled and governed by them. Territorial autonomy is what they want for and fight for, which can be seen in our state i.e. Jammu and Kashmir by the manifesto's of main political parties like National conference and People's

Democratic Party in the views of Autonomy and Self rule. The present circumstances made by the central authorities with their unilateral decision about the state without taking the main stream of the state's view about their decisions are seen highly depressed ones. It was against judgements that main political leaders have been booked behind bars, it is seen that these judgements made highly gloomy and saddened the main masses of the area. One of the major sense by which disintegration and disloyalty is produced in the country is the talk of town in the face of fake encounters, either they are or they are not but it is said by a greater number of masses. These things provide a greater chance in the way of conflicts in the land to get secession or withdraw from nation. The third category of conflicts is intended at larger share in the existing system and their demands are not at all intended at ethno nationalist claims. It is not essential that such claims are always confined to mere integration of their demands just because they are relatively weaker and cannot force upon the existing state system a separate homeland or autonomy for themselves. That may be because, it is not certain when the second category would turn into first category claims. Many a times, extreme demands in form of first category are also posed or advanced in order to negotiate and settle for the second one. Thus, the groups and communities start with a separate homeland demands but that is just the bargaining ploy/ tactics to force negotiation. They know their strength is not enough to achieve it. In such conditions, they really use it for greater control on resources and state decisions. Actually, the adherence to the demands depends on the strength of the community and relative weakness of the state to accept it. There can be chain in which the conflict arising at third level may subsequently turn into the third category. But it is possible only when the relative strength of the ethnic community is strong enough and there is support for such demands from outside the border especially in case of secessionism.

India is faced with all three kinds of conflicts and claims by people today. There are separate instances as well the conflicts which hold all three opinions. For example, take the case of Kashmir issue. There is no one opinion on the conflict. There are three streams within the conflict. There are those sections which are completely in understanding with Pakistan. And to them, resolution of Kashmir conflict lies in separation of Kashmir from India and its subsequent annexation with Pakistan. For them, Kashmir is illegally occupied by India as it is a Muslim majority province and therefore should go to Pakistan. There is another stream within the conflict which does not subscribe to the notion of switching over to Pakistan but seeks only a greater autonomy for the people. The official position of the National Conference, a party headed by Farooq Abdullah, which for greater part of post independent era has ruled the state and even today runs the government subscribes to this position only. There is a third section which does not want either of the two but wants economic development and protection of the civil and political rights of the people living in the state. This section comprises of a small section of the Muslim community apart from other groups. Needless to say the third section is a minuscule minority and does not carry much weight in the valley part of Kashmir. Similarly, demands of the Bodos in Assam in the North East though initiated with the demands for separate homeland but it actually aims at autonomy. Back in 80s, there was also a demand for Gorkhaland in West Bengal. It started with a secessionist note but ended with acceptance of Autonomous Hill Council and the arrangement has worked well so far. The newly elected government in West Bengal sorted out some of the issues which again were leading to second round of agitational politics in the region. The regional polarisation and caste based conflicts are aimed at greater share in the system. In the preceding two, the territorial monopoly is the intent whereas in the last one it is not. India, in fact, happens to be the breeding ground for ethnic conflicts and a test case for the ethnic studies by sheer diversity it holds. It would be beyond my comprehension to Hold that it alone encompasses this scale of diversity but certainly it is peculiar and distinct in many ways from other. When the British used the term 'Indian Subcontinent' to denote India their purpose was to inject the idea of existence of multiple nations in India. It was not just intended to depict the vast territorial geography.

In fact, they were confused by the diversity which marked the country not just in physical or geographical terrains but cultural, social and religious lines yet firming it together as a civilisational unit. This argument is valid as many scholars accept India as a successful democracy despite acute diversity across the country on caste, language and religious lines. With 24 recognised languages, over 2000 dialects many of which have the potential of being recognised as full-fledged languages, five major religions with over hundreds of sects and numerous sub-sects within the predominant religion Hinduism, thousands of castes and double of the same sub-castes, India has always been a challenging destinations for ethnographic studies. This diversity has been considered to be the single most asset of the civilisation, as many scholars propound that it has factored into yielding a stable polity, despite the fact that the division of the country in 1947 was based on the logic of religious distinctiveness and irreconcilable co-existence.

Ethnic Conflicts are very least in our country than European ones but greater autonomy and self rule sense is mostly seen, mainly in case of Jammu and Kashmir. In India, there are no ethnic conflicts strictly in European terms. Most of the European ethnic conflicts emerge from settling of migrated population which is either of different race, nationality or language groups or religion in some cases or combination of some of them or all. In India, there is no such case. If at all one finds such case it is the religious tension that has emerged from infiltration of the Muslim migrants from Bangladesh. Internal migration across provinces has also caused conflicts in recent years but that does not constitute a pattern and are limited to few parts of the country. Broadly speaking, one discerns six types of major conflicts in India today: Language based, caste based, religion based, region based, Inter-tribal conflicts or Tribal-plain conflicts in the North-East and the class conflicts led by the Maoists in conjunction with tribals against the state which is also supported by a big section of tribals, Maoists are driven by the ideology of class war and they have used the tribals and peasants displaced from their lands due to industrial activities in the remote forest areas in their struggle. The state has also responded by taking one section of the tribal against the Maoists. It arms them, trains them and provides all facilities in the fight against Maoism. This is a new initiative which aims at controlling the conflicts with the help of the citizens who are victim of the conflict. This emerged in the state of Chhattisgarh and is popularly known as Salwa Judum. The left extremism led by the Maoists has engulfed almost 352 police stations in six states of India and has been considered as one of the most dangerous challenges to internal security of the country. But this does not constitute part of this paper as it has little to do with the ethnic factors.

Regional polarisation of the communities is a recent phenomenon as specifically found in metropolis where there has been massive inter-state migration of population from underdeveloped and poor regions such as from Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Orissa and Bengal to industrially developed regions in search of job, manual or factory work, trade and education. The swelling strength of migrated population in some cases not only has changed the electoral dynamics of the state or the city but has also cut into the economic cleavages of the native people. In Mumbai, the grocery business, factory workers, auto-drivers are mainly controlled by the people from Bihar and Uttar Pradesh. Similarly, the plumbing, hand rickshaw, grocery business and the workers in the small industrial units are mainly the people from Orissa, Bihar and Uttar Pradesh in Delhi. Such migrations have unsettled the local electoral dynamics and have created tensions in the few regions. For example, in Maharashtra, the Champion of Hindutva, Raj Thakre unleashed a hatred campaign against the North-Indians in 2008 which resulted into violence in Mumbai and some other parts of Maharashtra, This was aimed at galvanising the Maharashtrians for political purpose, a strategy which the doyen of Shiv Sena, Balasaheb Thakre, applied in early 60s. Thakre used the 'Marathi Manus' concept, 'sons of the soil' to score points over Congress Party and succeeded also to an extent, though in subsequent decades he resorted to larger plank of Hindutva for electoral mobilisation. Such polarisation is also visible in case of Delhi where politicians have been using diatribe against the people from Bihar and Uttar Pradesh who from migration and settlement

have changed the demographic composition of the state. Being numerically dominant and quite capable of influencing the electoral fate of the parties there is almost negligible chance of Delhites engaging into conflicts with the people from Bihar, Uttar Pradesh and other states and there is a trend of now more and more accommodation of their cultural and linguistic aspirations. For example, the festival of Chhat, which is a religious festival, very popular and practised in the state of Bihar, was almost an unknown ceremony two decades back in Delhi. But now, the political parties which still are controlled by native Delhites are quite generous and accommodating on this count. They would be supporting in all measures and seem to be in race among each other to be seen as the biggest champion of the cause.

Language based conflicts have been yet another area of concern for the country. The linguistic conflicts have subsided to a great extent but it is not completely irrelevant and mortalised to ignite the emotions. The Language based conflicts appeared on large scale in post-independent India both in the North and the South. There was a vehement opposition to imposition of Hindi as a national language. The protest was more pronounced in South India, especially in Tamil Nadu where Dravidian Parties opposed it on the ground that this would place the Tamil speaking people in perpetual disadvantage in government jobs and public institutions compared to the Hindi belt regions. The first such movement against Hindi appeared in 1937. The Dravidian Parties and Justice Party opposed it when the government of Madras Presidency under the leadership of C. Rajgopalachari declared the inclusion of Hindi as essential subject in government schools, The opposition continued for almost three long years and it involved Dharna, demonstrations, fast, protest march etc. as also the violence which caused death of several people in the state. The second phase of the movement started again in 1948 when the then government of the Congress Party in Madras Presidency made Hindi as a compulsory language in schools and provisioned that a qualifying marks in Hindi was essential for promotion to higher classes. This again broke out in 1963 and could calm down only in 1967 when the Government of India brought out changes in the Official Language Act and almost ensured the continuity of English as official language, besides Hindi. English though symphonised with foreign language and was essentially a target during the freedom movement came out to be a preferred language over Hindi at least in the Southern India, especially in Tamil Nadu and Kerala. Even in the Constituent Assembly debates several members from the South had reservation on Hindi as a national language, though finally they agreed.

It is not that the conflicts have been only with regard to Hindi and English or Hindi vs. Tamil or Telugu but are the instances of inter-provincial conflicts on languages issues. For example, conflict in Assam in its early phase was directed against the Bengalis. Similarly, Belgaum still happens to be the bone of contention between the two provinces of India, Karnataka and Maharashtra. Conflicts often break out between the Marathi and Kannad speaking people. The nature of conflict is different across the states. Even the so called monolingual states have the ethnic conflicts. For example, once Telugu speaking people were united against the Tamil speaking and they fought for separate state. The movement resulted into conceding the demand of formation of the state of Andhra Pradesh. The language problem and related conflicts which witnessed large scale violence and protests all over country however started receding after declaration of three language' formula and carving out provinces for administrative management on the basis of linguistic contiguity after 1967 following the recommendations of the commission constituted for reorganisation of states. Therefore, there have not been frequent community conflicts on the basis of language in recent years. This does not mean to say that language issues have been resolved completely and in no way that carries the potential of conflicts among communities. They still hold capacity to ignite the society but they are not so powerful today to invoke conflicts singularly on their own.

Inter-tribes conflict of the North-East where tribes vs. tribes and sometime tribes vs. plain conflicts, as is the case with conflicts in Manipur, are on board. There is also not a singular pattern of conflicts in the North

East as well. The nature of conflict in Assam is different from the nature of conflicts in Manipur. Similarly conflicts in Nagaland are different from the rest. In Meghalaya the conflict is between the Khasis and the Nepalis. Khasis are tribals. Majority of them have been converted to Christianity. Nepalis are Hindus and they have resisted the proselytisation in their areas. This has often resulted into ethnic conflicts between the two as both have been positioning against each other for numerical and social dominance. Several times that has resulted into the violent conflicts between the two.

In Assam, the major reason behind the conflicts have been coming in of the people from non-Assamese speaking areas and changing the demographic, cultural, economic and political dynamics of the state. The Assamese movement was aimed at preservation of Assamese dominance in the territory of Assam. Quite obviously, it demanded for the expulsion of outsiders which included even Bengalis or Biharis'. But it was corrected and substituted by term foreigner in 1980 later on when Asom Sahitya Sabha indicated that it was not correct to expel even those who had been living in Assam for generations but were not originally Assamese. In the postindependent India, conflicts have emerged primarily from massive infiltration of people from Bangladesh who are mainly Muslims. According to an official estimate, nearly three crore Bangladeshis have infiltrated in to India and they are now staying in different parts of the country, mostly now equipped with election cards and ration cards which have brought them at par with any Indian citizen. The most affected states are Assam, West Bengal, Tripura, Bihar, UP, Maharashtra and Delhi. The police reports suggest that these infiltrators have not only caused law and order problem in different parts of the country by indulging in criminal and terrorist activities but have also brought in serious demographic changes in the bordering states. For example, the governor report on Assam suggests that the whole of Assam except the lower Brahmaputra Valley looks like Bangladesh'. And the Government of Bangladesh has been quoted of the policy of encouraging such infiltration in order to offload its own population. The cultural and linguistic proximity, porous international border, corruption on part of the border police (BSF), and most importantly support from the local Muslims in arranging ration cards and name on the electoral rolls could make it all possible. The Assamese launched a massive movement in mid eighties in which they demanded flushing out or expulsion of the outsiders from the state. Assam accord signed by the AGP and then Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi have failed to resolve the issue as the provision of detection of infiltrators and sending them back to Bangladesh has become a major political and ethno-religious issue in the country. While the right wing organisations have been insisting for deportation of the infiltrators who are mostly Muslims, the Muslim organisations have been providing shielding them because the increased numerical strength provides them the political power in the state. Muslim organisations are now in a position to dictate the terms to the political class and it is now impossible to push the infiltrators back to Bangladesh. In Assam, the conflict is not just between Assamese and outsiders but also between Bodos and Assamese speaking people. Bodos are the tribes who are now fighting for Bodoland. They claim to have a separate language and cultural heritage. Bodos are against their assimilation and absorption in the caste Hindu structure and they prefer their tribal roots including the culture and language over the Assamese language. In 1950 also they had demanded for separate territorial autonomy. The most crucial point is that it is in knowledge of every one from bordering state governments to the central government but they have failed to take any action due to political pressure from the Muslim organisations'. The social conflicts emerge out of the hierarchical divide within the Hindu community on caste lines and such conflicts are very frequent but operate at low scale. This has pan-Indian presence as phenomenon which often causes violence but the constituents of the conflicts are local as there is no pan-Indian caste configuration in hostile form. The conflicts do not engulf large areas even if the caste denominations engaged in the conflict are territorially spread over several provinces. These conflicts are result of deep rooted social, economic, educational and political deprivation of the backward and dalits in the society which now are seeking their

due in the System.

The religion based conflicts thus alone is the pan-Indian phenomenon. The religion driven conflicts are primarily between the Hindus and Muslims and between Hindus and Christians. There is rare conflict between the Muslims and Christians, Similarly there is absolutely no reportage of conflicts between Jews and Hindus. Hindu-Christians conflicts are not very violent and the primary reason of conflict lays at the proselytization of poor Hindus and tribals into Christianity. While the missionaries defend it on the ground that the constitution provides them the right to 'profess, practice and propagate' religion of his choice and conversion to their faith is part of this right the majority community condemn it on the ground that propagandising by use of unfair means is not a religious practice but a political design to outnumber the Hindus besides being antithetical to the spirit of the constitution which prohibits forced conversion. The Hindu-Muslim conflicts take a different shape as most of them are violent and a whole range of issues, from history to politics, cultural to political dominance, factor into the conflict.

Conclusion:

It is the need of hour to listen the genuine requests of people in the world so that it would minimise the conflict senses among the masses. In order to calm the evils of ethnic divide and conflicts arising out of such divide solution does not lie in encouraging and accepting it as the basis of policy but rejecting it as 'a basis of policy without rejecting the ethnic identity of a society. Acceptance of group identity as the basis of social policy nurtures and strengthens further the group identity and group solidarity which always seeks its preponderance vis a vis other groups. Caste identity two decades back had few takers. Those who earlier deterred from their caste identity and used to attach upper caste surname are now vocal about their castes. Not only this, the upper castes are lobbying and pressurising the government to be placed in the backward caste to derive the benefit of reservation whereas the backward castes are agitating for their pushed down into the SC categories. Facts and figures are being dug out to prove their points. Caste based reservation has strengthened the caste identity and has legitimised it and made it an integral part of the society rather than eradicating the malaise of caste. While the constitution discourages caste based politics and aspires to achieve a casteless society politics of caste has made it a permanent feature of the society more strengthened and institutionalised than ever. Political parties have been careful enough in fielding the candidates in the elections on the basis of numerical dominance of the caste. What has resulted from it is that the castes are pitted against each other. Gurjar and Meena conflicts in Rajasthan, Jats agitation in Uttar Pradesh and Haryana, are case to the point. The identity based policies which otherwise are denounced only strengthen the identities. Democracy has worked towards new identity formation. In order to consolidate the community identity there is a trend towards more and more drawing towards factor which constitutes the identity. For example, Urdu language is not very popular in the southern states except for some parts of Andhra Pradesh. But Muslim organisations have started campaigning from door to door to see that during census all Muslims should tick Urdu as their mother language.

Neither the power sharing nor the power dividing mechanisms are on their own solution to the ethnic conflicts. Further, no mechanism can lay claim of resolving the conflicts completely and produce a conflict free society. The only point is how to minimise the intensity of the conflict and how to manage it in a fashion that it does not escalate into ethno-nationalist demands. Two theoretical points are worth consideration. First, there is a need to restore the primacy of the individual rights and freedoms, and any ethnic claim that seeks to govern and regulate the former needs to be discouraged and curbed. Two, there cannot be one formula to deal with whole range of ethnic conflicts across the world. That is going to vary from country to country depending upon the whole set of variables that come into play to decide ethnic conflicts in a diverse society. There can

be multiple alternatives or strategies that need to be worked out suitable to the conditions that prevail but the bottom line is that no such attempts should be encouraged which allow the ethnic leaders to dictate terms to the political leadership. Every ethnic community claims to have right to govern entire community domain, from religious rituals to social, cultural and political space. It seeks to appropriate all in name of protecting community interests. If it is allowed to happen, then the political domain will be narrowed down. Modern society is not all about political democracy and political leadership led and governed by the ethnic leaders but vice versa. Allowing more and more space to the ethnic demands as a mechanism of accommodation of minority rights in form of consociationalism and allowing ethnisation of nation's domain is really alarming and a potential threat to the liberal democracy framework which we all cherish about.

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